

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF ENERGY ABSORPTION IN WOVEN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The aim of the paper is to submit experimental and numerical results on energy absorption behaviour of woven composite plates submitted to high dynamic tensile. The hybrid woven plate (glass - kevlar - epoxy) is clamped at one end and impacted at the other end in order to obtain damage and failure of the sample. Usual finite element method programs with damage theories are unable to give a correct numerical answer to this problem. We show that a modified Chang's ([1], [2], [3]) progressive damage theory including new post failure rules can be used to compute the response of the sample and to obtain good numerical results on the energy absorbed by the sample.

KEYWORDS: hybrid woven composite, dynamic, failure, energy absorption

INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in crashworthy structures offers significant weight and cost reduction relative to metal structures. In the last decade, several authors ([4], [5], [6]) have shown by crushing tests on composite tubes the ability of composite materials to absorb energy. In spite of the considerable work done in experimental studies, reliable numerical models are not yet available to predict the energy absorption behaviour of composite structures. The aim of this study is to simulate this phenomenon in the case of composite plates by using a dynamic finite element software [7]. The woven composite constitutive law is obtained from an experimental study. Dynamic behaviour is described and the typical load displacement curve shows the ability of the woven to absorb energy. A first finite element model based on Chang's theory shows that the failure rules are inadequate to describe energy absorption. New damage rules are introduced to solve failure progression in the plate. It is shown that load carried capacity of the plate is in good agreement with experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material data

The material used in this investigation is a glass - kevlar- epoxy woven composite. The tested structure is made of height ply of twill weave as shown on Fig 1.

Fig.1: Twill weave.

The samples (Fig.2) are cut from twill panels and submitted to quasi-static tensile load in order to derive in-plane elastic constitutive law [8]. Table 1 summarizes fiber volume fraction and elastic properties of the studied structure.

Fig. 2 : geometry of the studied sample.

E_{11}	σ_{11}^r	ϵ_{11}^r	ν_{12}	G_{12}
13400 MPa	156 MPa	1.16 %	0.20	2040 MPa

Table 1

Dynamic Tensile Test.

The dynamic test on the sample was carried on the cutted sample [8]. One end is clamped and the other end is impacted by a rigid body with velocity V (Fig 3).

Fig.3: Schematic view of testing machine.

Velocity is chosen to obtain damage and the final breaking of the structure. Different values of the velocity (10.5, 15, 20.5, 25 m/s) were applied to the rigid body. We have only deal with the third case of velocity.

Experimental Results.

Displacement is recorded at one end of the sample whereas load carried by structure is at the other end. The pattern of failed sample and the load displacement curve are shown in Fig 4 and Fig 5. The scheme of Fig 4 shows that damage occurs only in a localised zone behind initial cutting.

Fig. 4: Failed sample with localised damage zone

Fig.5: Load - displacement curves for static and dynamic experiments.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Constitutive Relations of Laminates.

The woven structure is considered to have an inelastic behaviour. As described by ([9],[10],[11],[12]), the non linearities between shear stresses and shear strains are more important than non linearities between normal stresses and normal strains. This behaviour is taken into account by the following relation suggested by Tsai [11]:

$$2\varepsilon_{12} = \frac{\tau_{12}}{G_{12}} + \alpha \cdot \tau_{12}^3 \quad (1)$$

where ε_{12} and τ_{12} are respectively strain and shear components, G_{12} is the shear modulus and α is a material constant. We assume plane stress state in this study and use the usual laminated theory to derive constitutive equations of the plate which are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{21} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \text{ or, } \{\sigma\} = [S]^{-1} \{\varepsilon\} = [Q]\{\varepsilon\} \quad (2)$$

with,

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} \quad Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{12} = \frac{E_1 \cdot \nu_{21}}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} = \frac{E_2 \cdot \nu_{12}}{1 - \nu_{12} \cdot \nu_{21}} = Q_{21}, Q_{66} = G_6 \quad (4)$$

thus:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Chang's degradation rules are used to take into account progressive failure in composites.

Finite element model and numerical results with Chang's model.

The finite element discretization uses Belytschho [13] shell elements. Several computations were done and the results on the mesh size have shown that the optimum number of shells was about 480. Numerical results with Chang's damage rules are given on Fig 6:

Fig. 6 : First numerical and experimental results for the sample

Fig.7 : Evolution of normal stresses

The load curve versus displacement shows pic values which are similar to experimental results, but maxima values of stresses are too high and energy absorber is not completely described.

A new theory of damage and post failure in woven composites.

Since Chang criterion tends to overload the strength of the woven composite in the case of dynamic loading and to undervalue energy absorption, we have implemented in LS-DYNA3D software [7], a maximum stress limit and new post degradation rules which are based on the hypothesis that the failure of fibers in tensile is the predominant mode of failure. The loss of woven stiffness in filler and stuffer weavers is governed by two different parameters a_c and a_t . The usual constitutive relations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{xx}}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{E_{yy}\nu_{xy}}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ \frac{E_{xx}\nu_{yx}}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{E_{yy}}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

are replaced by the new law:

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_c \cdot E_{xx} & a_t \cdot E_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Numerical results are now closely connected with experimental data (Fig.8). Let us tell that our results are here given without any filter. We can therefore state that post failure behaviour of woven composite structures can be numerically taken into account in the treatment of crash response of energy absorption components.

Fig.8 : Carried load versus displacement

CONCLUSION

Behaviour up to failure in woven composites subjected to high dynamic tensile can be well modelled by a modified Chang's progressive damage theory. Numerical results concerning an hybrid woven composites (glass - kevlar - epoxy) are in good agreement with experimental data. The post-failure behaviour of composite structures can be numerically obtained by using finite element method. Numerical solutions can be taken into account in the treatment of crash response of energy absorption components.

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